

FEATURES OF THE LOGISTICS PROCESS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *The article examines the features of the logistics process in oil and gas industry, which is a complex and multifaceted system for managing the movement of hydrocarbon raw materials. These features make logistics in oil and gas industry unique and require a specialized approach to ensure its efficiency and sustainability.*

Keywords: *logistics process, oil and gas industry, features of oil and gas industry*

INTRODUCTION

The oil and gas industry is one of the key sectors of the global economy, playing an important role in ensuring energy security and economic development. The logistics process in oil and gas industry is a complex system of organizing and managing the flow of materials, equipment and information at all stages of hydrocarbon production, transportation and processing.

The relevance of studying the features of the logistics process in oil and gas industry is due not only to its importance for the global economy, but also to a number of specific challenges and problems that enterprises in this industry face. In this article, we will consider the key aspects of the logistics process in oil and gas industry and analyze the challenges that companies in this industry face.

The oil and gas industry handles a wide variety of cargo, including materials in gaseous, liquid, and solid states. This makes the job of logisticians in this industry more complex than their counterparts who work exclusively with containerized cargo. Logisticians in the oil and gas industry are involved in the procurement, loading, transportation, storage, and distribution of various commodities, including liquefied natural gas and gasoline.

The geography of their activities, climatic conditions and distances require them to update constantly their knowledge not only in the areas mentioned above, but also in the field of cargo science. Today, the oil and gas industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan is of great importance for the economy of the entire country. In the structure of the country's primary fuel and energy resources, 97% are oil and gas, 2.3% are coal, and 0.7% are hydropower. [1] The oil and gas industry, which employs approximately 1% of the country's employed population, is one of the main sources of GDP, budget revenues and foreign exchange earnings, and also plays a significant role in the structure of industrial production and attracting investment. [1] It is precisely this that provides opportunities for economic development, comfortable living for people, and the creation of conditions for the normal functioning of priority sectors of the economy. However, it is already impossible today to maintain the huge oil and gas infrastructure in normal working order, and even more so to increase the volumes of natural gas production, satisfying the needs of the population and the economy of the country without transferring the sphere to the rails of a market economy.

METHODS

This article uses statistical and factor analysis methods to quantify data and identify trends and patterns in logistics processes. Factor analysis, in turn, helps identify hidden variables that affect logistics efficiency and group related factors to simplify the interpretation of results.

RESULTS

The oil and gas industry is strategically important for the development of the economy of Uzbekistan. The growth of the economy over the past 5 years and the expansion of production capacity have led to an increase in the demand for energy resources, which makes this industry one of the priority areas of development.

The main activity in this area in the period from 2017 to 2022 was aimed at expanding production capacity, attracting foreign investment and increasing oil and gas production, as well as increasing the share of alternative energy sources in the country's energy balance. However, if we analyze the dynamics of oil production, gas condensate and production of petroleum products, we can see a downward trend in production (Figure 1).

Thus, over the period 2017-2022, oil production decreased by 3.2%, gas condensate production decreased by 34.1%.

Figure 1. Dynamics of oil production and production of petroleum products in the period of 2010-2022. Source: [2]

The production of diesel, jet fuel, and aviation gasoline also decreased by 12.1%, 2.4%, and 98%, respectively. Over the past 5 years, only gasoline production increased by 13.2% and fuel oil by 14.3%. [2] The same situation is observed for natural gas (Figure 2) - thus, natural gas production decreased by 8.8% over 5 years, but consumption increased by 5.4%. [2]

However, it is worth understanding that a thorough analysis is necessary to identify reserves for increasing the efficiency of country's oil and gas sector. Thus, logistics is one of the most important components of the oil and gas industry. The oil and gas industry itself has many features due to the large number of stages for obtaining finished products from raw materials. In view of this, the logistics process itself has its own features. Logistics in the oil and gas industry is a specialized area that includes the transportation of hazardous materials, large equipment, and complex operations such as transporting large quantities of cargo in a short time during the winter and summer delivery to hard-to-reach places. In order to successfully develop logistics in companies, it is necessary to understand the features of logistics processes and functions. Let's consider the main ones.

1. *Compliance with safety and environmental protection.* After a number of serious accidents in the world, the work of oil companies, both themselves and their contractors, is unthinkable without strict safety and environmental protection requirements. According to Rostekhnadzor on April 22, 2021, 44 accidents occurred in the oil and gas industry in Russia alone in 2020. Therefore, any logistics and transport contractor working in the oil and gas sector must have a safety program when providing services to oil and gas companies. Oil companies have their own requirements for performing work at oil fields, and as a result, they establish their own additional safety rules for logistics and transport operations, cargo loading and unloading areas, and material handling and assembly areas. Logistics and transport contractors must study them and strictly follow them when providing services. [8]

Figure 2. Dynamics of production and consumption of natural gas in the period of 2010 – 2022. Source: [2]

2. *Carrying out transport and logistics work in hard-to-reach and remote places and harsh climatic conditions.* It is common knowledge that deposits are searched for and developed where there is virtually no infrastructure. Therefore, this greatly complicates and increases the cost of transporting materials and supplies. Often, vehicles that deliver cargo to warehouses and deposits of oil and gas companies are used inefficiently, as they return empty from unloading sites and have a large number of empty runs. As a result, efficient logistics is the most sought-after service for oil and gas companies when delivering cargo. [7]

3. *Complex supply chains,* including a large number of suppliers, a wide range of products, multiple pick-up locations, and opaque supply chains. Companies that relied on their suppliers and did not control their supply chains, were unable to receive goods on time, or quickly find new sources, were hit the hardest during the pandemic. As the analysis of conference materials on supply of oil and gas complex enterprises shows, the organization of purchasing processes, selection of supplier, etc., i.e. everything that forms the link, now designated as supply logistics, is increasingly becoming the object of close attention of company management, the subject of improvement and various reorganizations. The experience accumulated by oil and gas companies in recent years in organizing the purchase of various products and services shows that the theoretical premises of the market in the "demand-supply" system remain largely theoretical. The theory does not cover such important components as, for example, the choice of a supplier, which is selected based on non-market factors very often. Over the past 10-15 years, oil and gas

companies have practically switched to a centralized procurement system, despite the geographical dispersion of their enterprises. Such seemingly not so important types of activities of departments as document processing, organization of tenders, etc. also lead to procurement costs. In addition, a modern supplier must have a very high level of training, both theoretical and practical. For example, a procurement department employee must know the principles of product pricing and navigate the markets. Quite a high level of costs is explained by errors made due to a lack of knowledge of Incoterms-2010. [8] Therefore, the use of innovative and digital supply chains is the main direction for increasing their efficiency and transparency in the oil and gas sector. Contract logistics solves many problems for oil and oilfield service companies. In order for a logistics and transport contractor to integrate quickly into the supply chains of oil and gas companies, ensuring the reliability and transparency of its services, it needs to know the main features of transport and logistics support for cargo in the oil and gas complex and effectively use them in its work.

4. *Losses of oil and oil products along the entire route from the well to the end consumer*, be it a petrol station, petrochemical complex, export terminal or oil depot. Despite ongoing efforts to reduce these losses, there are currently no relevant statistics or information on programs to improve the situation covering key segments of oil and gas production. Various sources provide different estimates of oil and oil product losses within the specified supply chain. For example, the total losses are 9.5%: 4.0% at oil fields, 3.5% at refineries, and 2.0% during transportation and storage at oil depots and oil product pipelines. Other sources indicate total losses of 10%, including up to 2.2% at oil fields, up to 2.5% during transportation, about 3.5% at refineries, and 1.8% at oil depots and gas stations. As you can see, there is a noticeable difference, even 0.5% of the total production of 550 million tons is approximately 2.75 million tons per year, which is equal to almost half a year of oil refining at combined LK-6u units. This difference of 0.5% probably occurs due to the use of different accounting methods. [7]

5. *Distribution logistics*. Significant opportunities for cost reduction are associated with this area. This is a rather unique area, requiring specialized knowledge in marketing. When forming a distribution logistics strategy, a company should focus on two key aspects:

- deep study of market needs;
- application of new technologies to meet identified needs through effective management of distribution networks and logistics services. Large losses, including violations of legislation, occur at the final stages of interaction between the manufacturer and the consumer. Thus, due to insufficient control over the activities of the distribution link - the company's gas stations - serious violations occur that affect the safety of the flow of goods along its route from beginning to end. [8]

6. *Inventory logistics*. Inventory is one of the most expensive assets of most companies operating in the field of mining and processing of minerals. As a rule, the share (by value) of inventory in the invested capital is 38-40%. The main costs that a company is forced to incur in connection with the creation and maintenance of inventory in its own or rented warehouses are as follows. Firstly, we are talking about frozen financial resources. Inventory stored in the company's warehouses costs money. Money spent on purchasing stored products, on already produced semi-finished products, etc., do not bring new money and "become more expensive" every day, because they do not work. Furthermore, the company must incur expenses related to the maintenance of warehouses and areas, and it is necessary to pay for the work of service personnel. With sufficiently long storage, spoilage of goods and theft occur. In the oil and gas industry, as in other

industries, there is a problem of illiquid assets. These are stocks that have been stored in warehouses for a long time in the form of finished products or raw materials. They mainly arise due to changes in production technology, or equipment or various components were supplied for a project that was later suspended for some reason, or errors occurred when forming an order, as a result of which the volumes of purchases were incorrectly determined, as well as due to irregular or seasonal needs. In some cases, cargo arrives incomplete, defective or damaged during transportation. Here, it is worth noting the errors of supply departments.

CONCLUSION. The logistics process in the oil and gas industry is unique and complex. This is due to a number of factors, including the geographic location of sources, the complexity of transportation, and strict safety and environmental standards. However, despite these complexities, effective logistics management can lead to significant improvements in operational efficiency and cost reduction. This, in turn, can increase the competitiveness of companies in this industry. It is important to note that innovation and technological advancement continue to play a key role in optimising logistics processes in the oil and gas industry, becoming an integral part of the strategy of oil and gas companies, allowing them to adapt to market changes, increase the sustainability of their operations and achieve new levels of efficiency. In the future, we can expect further technological advancements that will contribute to even greater improvements in logistics processes in this key industry.

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